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Market Pathways for Cloud Edge IoT in Mobility Sector

White paper

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1 Digital transformation of the mobility sector

The digitalisation of the recent years has opened up a new quality transportation technology based on the underlying innovations in information and communication technology. In fact, new trends in information technology have made existing services more efficient and triggered the market for a bunch of new services and functions in all relevant domains mentioned above, especially focussed on automation based on a strong flow of more or less permanently collected real-time data. The technical possibilities for data collection have increased in dimensions.

The key trends were ever-increasing computing and networking power, distributed software architectures, the availability of high-performance mobile communications, the ubiquitous availability of flexible mobile devices, including smartphones, new sensors and the Internet of Things (IoT), which is making all kinds of objects intelligent. Further factors are the ever-increasing ability to capture, exchange and process data in real time as well as the existence of data hubs and access points. Important trends are also the deployment of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML) as well as Digital Twins (DT) to represent and model real-world processes with the possibility to influence them online and to make predictions. Last but not least, Cloud Computing enabled centralised data processing using centralised computing as a service whereas Edge Computing partly reversed this trend optimising data traffic.

This new quality of digitalisation supports new market trends in transportation by enabling new technical solutions which promote a high quality, efficiency, performance and safety of transport and mobility. The following examples demonstrate the current revolutionary changes in transportation technology: In the automotive industry, the Software-defined Vehicle (SDV) approach contributes to efficient vehicle development, operation and optimisation. New technologies support the further implementation of green vehicles and automated driving. AI technologies support traffic data detection and their processing in a new generation of multi-modal agent-based traffic management systems. Shared transport services (car/ bike/ scooter sharing, ride sharing) are built on modern fleet management and booking systems. Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) platforms are built on data sharing possibilities and on the co-operation of multiple stakeholders in public transport and shared transport services. Ships will in future be automatically or remotely operated controlled without crews on board. Supply Chain Management (SCM) systems will be automated across companies. In future, even more disruptive approaches like Hyperloop and driverless air taxis, which are partly still subject to R&D, will depend only highly automated approaches.

Due to the fact that the "Mobility" sector as such is in reality a wide area which covers many different applications and use cases in different fields it is hard to cover all upcoming innovations. So we will focus on selected important examples for consideration in the following chapters in order to characterise the main market pathways for Cloud-Edge-IoT in the mobility sector.

2 Specific Challenges for Cloud Edge IoT in the Mobility Sector

Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) technologies in the mobility sector have the potential to support highly automated processes which depend on continuous, high volume data flows. The applications usually depend on comprehensive sensor sets which continuously provide process data which are then used in real-time by intelligent algorithms for data analysis. This may involve Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Digital Twins using high performance computing etc. in order to perform analytic tasks online which again influence the respective processes in the real world using actors performing control decisions, providing information or giving software updates for local units. For the Mobility Sector, this opens wider perspectives. Especially the transportation and traffic-related processed feature a wide range of mobile objects (vehicles, passengers, travellers, goods, transport units etc.) which can deliver data and which may be integrated in real-time information on their state to be used in intelligent data processing on a larger scale.

At this stage, we would like to list some specific key features of the mobility sector which should guide the design of CEI systems. However, due to the fact that mobility is a vast functional domain, concrete requirements can only define for concrete use cases. So, at this point we can only point on some the sector-specific factors which will influence, trigger or inhibit the adoption of CEI applications:

- **Efficiency by flexible process automation:** The use of CEI applications are supposed to contribute to a more efficient traffic and transport network operation, to a more efficient design of vehicles, infrastructures and processes and to more efficient logistics. Economic viability and cost efficiency is key for the success of technology. The CEI-based technologies must provide a clear added value and must be operated at a competitive price and promise clear added value in comparison with the state-of-play.
- **Safety:** Transport and traffic safety is a key factor in a wide range of transport-related applications. The CEI technologies must contribute to safe traffic and transport operations and the ambition is that they make transport systems safer in a significant way. This especially means for CEI systems that data processing with AI, ML, simulations, Digital Twins, which often interfere with traffic and transport in real-time, must be highly reliable, plausible and failure-safe.
- **Data Protection, Security and Privacy, System Resilience:** Cyber-security is a basic requirement to transport-related systems and the ambition increases with the degree of networking and automation. If it comes to individual transport users, the protection of their privacy becomes important. In relation to transport systems prevention of cyber-attacks, provoked accidents and catastrophes and data misuse must be guaranteed.
- **Clear governance and regulations:** The mobility sector is strongly influenced by the division into a public and a private domain. Especially in the urban areas, but also in regional and inter-urban road transport we find public structures whereas e.g. logistics and the automotive sector are privately dominated. As many CEI systems build upon co-operative approaches, public-private regulations for open interfaces and standards, open data, data spaces, data exchange and access points, data quality, protection of commercial interests are important.

The deployment of CEI approaches has – in some respects – the potential to directly satisfy these requirements quite well. Efficiency, for example, especially in comparison with mere cloud applications can be enabled by keeping system functions on edge components near the sensing equipment which reduces data traffic and processing costs and makes communication faster. Security can be increased if traffic data volumes from and to the cloud are reduced by edge architectures.

3 Approach and analysis methodology

In the following, we would like to illustrate which innovative solutions and Cloud-Edge-IoT technologies are already available on the market or use cases which are being planned. To understand the current state of this transformation process, we will look in to the CEI market dynamics in the Mobility Sector. In particular we want to answer the following research questions:

- 🏠 Who are the big tech players in the CEI market and which services do they offer?
- 🏠 How do the big tech CEI players co-operate with big players from the Mobility Sector?
- 🏠 Which players in the Mobility sector provide new innovative solutions? And how do these solutions contribute to the transformation in the Mobility Sector?
- 🏠 Where are the major dependencies from the big tech players and the resulting risks? What are market pathways and opportunities for CEI companies in the Mobility Sector?
- 🏠 Are CEI and Mobility markets ready for data sharing?
- 🏠 Where can development gaps be identified?
- 🏠 How are European companies positioned in the market?
- 🏠 What are the business opportunities for SMEs and start-ups?
- 🏠 How are the chances for open source applications and open standardised interface?

Together with our partners IDC and Bluspecs, we identified basic building blocks that depict possible Cloud-Edge-IoT configurations for the technical infrastructures and services (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Cloud-Edge-IoT Building Blocks – Source: UnlockCEI

Each of these building blocks represents a domain that may require significant development and innovation to enable widespread adoption of the applications in the CEI continuum. These functional building blocks are distributed over the components whole CEI chain and this scheme will help in the analysis of use cases hereafter.

4 CEI infrastructure providers and the market dynamics in the mobility sector

The investigation of the Cloud-Edge-IoT topic on the demand side in the mobility sector has shown that a wide range of applications is already on the market and further solutions is under development. The potential of data-driven solutions for the optimisation processes based on intelligent solutions using AI, high-performance computing, Digital Twins has been recognised in all application fields in the mobility sector. This concerns the planning, operation as well as the maintenance of processes and systems.

In all cases, the main market driver seems to be the supply side which offers the sector-specific IT solutions and not necessarily the end user. Concerning the CEI and Edge technologies, the drivers seem to be sector-specific IT companies which provide Edge solutions for transport/mobility-related problems. They have discovered data-driven approaches, AI and ML as a means to advance their sector-specific IT products. For the cloud-related part of the solution, co-operation is sought with a cloud service provider. This may be one of the well-known global hyperscalers. Also examples for co-operations with European cloud providers like Bosch IoT, SAP or Hetzner can be found. Also, the establishment of new local cloud services is an option.

It can be observed that the Big-tech Players in the cloud market like AWS, Microsoft Azure, IBM, Bosch IoT are also dominant in the mobility market. On the cloud level a sector-wise specialisation can rarely be observed, although the hyperscalers all tend to provide cloud solutions for wider range of sectors. This is different on the edge-level where specialised sector-specific players like Yunex, consider it, Continental or Bosch can be found more often. Reasons for this is probably sector-specific IT know-how and traditionally existing market presence and this may be one of their main advantages in the competition with pure cloud providers, apart from the general advantages of edge computing. An exception is Pratexo, a successful international IT start-up in Edge computing which is present in multiple sectors. When discussing specific user requirements for a particular application, end users from the mobility sector come into play.

4.1 Innovative solutions for more efficiency and safety in a smart mobility system

In the following chapters, we will provide information about use cases in the Mobility Sector which are already in deployment or which are being development as part of research and development activities. Some of them, which have been subject to our interviews and workshops in UNLOCK CEI, will then be further analysed in chapter 4.2 ff., also in the light of the above mentioned research questions.

So we observed for example the following existing CEI use cases which are in everyday operation:

- 🏠 C-ITS (Co-operative Intelligent Transport) services for connected and automated driving as a basis for AI-based traffic simulation and digital twins urban traffic management*
- 🏠 SPaT (Signal Phase and Timing) boxes in signal control for AI-based interpretation of signalisation phases in road traffic signalisation
- 🏠 Camera-based traffic data detection software for real-time traffic data detection and traffic management services
- 🏠 Camera-based checking of containers for damages at transshipment terminals in seaports.

Other CEI use cases are in preparation and about to be implemented:

- 🏠 Automotive edge platforms for software-defined vehicles (SDV)*
- 🏠 Supply chain management (SCM) in freight transport concerning in the aerospace industry*

- 🏠 Automated control of vessels without crew in maritime transport*
 - 🏠 Online monitoring of the maintenance needs for railway overhead wires
- (Use cases marked with * are more deeply analysed hereafter.)

4.2 Innovative solution by Continental and AWS: Automotive edge framework for software-defined vehicles (SDV)

Use Case: Software-defined Vehicle (SDV)

The Software-Defined Vehicle (SDV) is a new concept in the automotive industry for an innovative system architecture in relation to all electronic control, information and management functions of a vehicle. Sensors and actuators in a vehicle are integrated in one common vehicle-based, scalable high-performance edge platform which manages the operative functions locally in a single vehicle.

This includes real-time data collection and the operative control of all electronic devices in the vehicle. The full range of electronically controlled functions is covered: control functions for devices in the cockpit, control of electronic systems in the car body, the safety systems, the control of the powertrain, the external communication, the Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) as well as automated driving functions.

The automotive software platform processes vehicle-related functions locally in the vehicle, but data for simulation and validation is uploaded to the cloud, where cloud services in a data centre work to optimise vehicle software by analysing incoming data from connected vehicles of a particular make and model. Digital twins of the vehicle support software development and predictive maintenance. A workbench provides software and vehicle developers at OEMs and their suppliers with a toolchain for monitoring, analysing, developing and adapting vehicle functions.

It is a main advantage of this architectural configuration that the functionality of the electronic devices in the vehicle can be modified simply by downloading software updates. Software can be delivered and changed continually when the vehicle is already sold and in the field. This will – in future – be enabled by a service-oriented architecture where central high-performance computers (HPC) control all edge devices in the vehicle. On-board systems can then be re-configured in such a way that the whole “product vehicle” can permanently be further enhanced after sales and during everyday operation. Likewise, the vehicles can selectively collect data which is uploaded and centrally used by data analytics for the further optimisation of vehicle configuration and vehicle control.

Figure 2: Continental Automotive Edge (CAEdge) Framework – Source: Continental

The figure above shows the CEI architecture of the Continental Automotive Edge (CAEdge) Framework as an example for an SDV architecture, which is offered by Continental in co-operation with AWS and Elektrobit.

Observations on Market Pathways:

A typical ecosystem supporting the commercialisation of the SDV concept requires the cooperation of stakeholders traditionally involved in the production of Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) with specialists in centralised computing and cloud computing. The latter group consists mainly of the well-known global hyperscalers, e.g. AWS, where European stakeholders are in the minority. The more vehicle-related central computing functions are often provided by sector-specific players such as Bosch, Continental, ZF, Aptiv or Elektrobit. In this area, European presence is obvious. European players can benefit from sector-specific expertise in the automotive sector.

In interviews and workshops with stakeholders, we could identify furthermore the following which relevant to SDV market dynamics. The CAEdge Framework is example for a cooperation of EU (Continental, Elektrobit) and US (AWS) big tech partners. AWS provides know-how with customized cloud services. Continental contributes with vehicle electronics-related know-how and hardware and software components on the micro (on-device) edge (in the car). Main advantage of the framework is a **parallel** and therefore efficient **development of hardware and software that accelerates innovation cycles. This saves time and costs in the development process.**

The CAEdge Framework provides a development environment for the SDV. This environment is at the same time a **co-operation platform for stakeholders** who are involved in the vehicle development. This concerns the vehicle manufacturers as well as suppliers, including **SMEs**. As part of the CAEdge Framework the Continental Cooperation Platform (CCP) enables the co-operation of different software suppliers. This process must be orchestrated and quality-monitored.

We can clearly see the relation to the basic **building blocks for the CEI Continuum** introduced in chapter 3 **Digital Twins** which simulate vehicle electronics in the Cloud are the most important building blocks in the computing continuum. They provide the possibility to simulate, test and even certify vehicle electronics using the cloud computing environment. Thus, they allow parallel hardware and software development.

Storage and data pipelines support the simulation (e.g. for testing the ADAS functions of the vehicle) in the Cloud.

AI in the Cloud is, for example, used to check detected against test data in order to approve new software updates. This functionality is integrated in die **CEI continuum** by the uplink of vehicle-related real-time data from vehicle-based edge platform and the download of software updates to the vehicles.

Open interfaces are not yet implemented and not all interfaces will be open. **Data sharing of vehicle data will be most likely not possible.** Field data from vehicles will remain in the vehicle also in the future.

Furthermore the following observations concerning the use case can be reported:

Start-ups which collect and sell vehicle data have not yet been commercially successful in this context. Today, user experience generates the highest value proposition, e.g. usability of entertainment systems will be crucial for buying decisions. The current automotive technology is almost the same for the most vendors and OEMs. The **value of vehicle** data has largely been over-estimated as far as the potential for new business is concerned. It is depending on the specific business case to generate added value.

European large-scale pilots in the context of SDVs should concentrate on building and demonstrating open interfaces between cloud-based development environments and tool chains for **different** OEMs and suppliers as well as standardisation of data sharing formats for seamless integration of tool chains. It would be important to open the interfaces to cloud-based tools

because currently every OEM has own products. This would decrease the high effort of suppliers for integration.

Data sharing efforts in the framework of CATENA X are already a first success, but open solutions for the collection of vehicle data is still an issue.

Industry Associations like ECLIPSE and SOAFEE support the development of standards and open source solutions in the field of SDV. The Gaia-X4Ageda project brings the automotive edge activities into the Gaia-X ecosystem. The project CeCas in Germany is dealing with the use of open RISC-V and other hardware technologies to support future central car servers, what is a further precondition for the successful implementation of HPC in cars.

The efficient implementation of the SDV approach needs the **co-operation of OEMs** involving all necessary Tier 1 und Tier 2 suppliers. It is a co-operative task. The EU project FEDERATE supports the co-operation based on a new common overall architecture and a roadmap for the implementation.

Continental looks positively at **the co-operation with the Hyperscaler AWS**. The cloud services have been developed in close co-operation.

4.3 Innovative Solution by consider it: C-ITS services for connected and automated driving

Use Case: C-ITS

A further use case for CEI architectures is Co-operative Intelligent Transport (C-ITS) systems. This is a family of road traffic management applications on the basis of a mobile data communication between road vehicles and the intelligent roadside traffic control infrastructure (V2I), between vehicles (V2V) or between any other equipped road users (V2N). This type of communication enables a wider range of traffic management services involving connected vehicles. The first generation of these services is now being rolled out worldwide. These services enlarge the range of advanced driver assistance and traffic management applications based on the availability of information from roadside traffic control infrastructure and from other vehicles, also in real-time or near real-time. Examples for these services are: priority requests for public transport and emergency vehicles, green-time prognoses at traffic lights, various types of hazard warnings, collection of data from vehicles, in-vehicle traffic signing, speed harmonisation etc. Data is collected and distributed on the far edge by vehicle on-board units (OBU) and roadside units located at roadside control equipment (RSU). Data processing for traffic management purposes is done in an on-premise edge unit, whereas cloud-based solutions generate an online traffic situation overview and provide analysis functions concerning the C-ITS services, nowadays also using AI tools, e.g. to generate agent-based traffic prognoses. Collected data can also be provided to external users via open interfaces. In the figure below the product of the German SME consider it is show, which offers a complete family of components for C-ITS services.

Figure 3: The consider it C-ITS System – Source: consider it

Observations on Market Pathways:

- 🏠 The solution Communication in Traffic (CiT) uses OBU and RSUs as well as edge servers and software modules which were developed by the German information technology company consider it. The central tools for data analysis and system management are cloud-based. For hosting and cloud services consider it sought co-operations with cloud service providers. We have here an example for CEI value chain which is fully operated by European stakeholders.
- 🏠 The systems is built upon European standards for data communication in the field of C-ITS (mainly elaborated by ETSI).
- 🏠 The system provides traffic data to other data platforms and access points on urban, national and European level using standard formats, e.g. to the Hamburg Urban Data Platform, the German national access point for traffic data (mobilithek) and the European Platform for C-ITS services (C-ROADS). This again, supports the generation Digital Twins of the traffic situation and short-time traffic prognosis for whole urban areas.
- 🏠 The main users for the systems are public road authorities in municipalities and in regions, but also public transport companies and private individual drivers.
- 🏠 The requirement that traffic-related data needs to be open and openly published on public data space is more and more subject to procurement contracts with public authorities and contracts for project funded by public authorities. This way private provides can be encouraged to provide data publicly.

4.4 Innovative Solution by Hanse Aerospace: Supply Chain Management (SCM) in freight transport concerning in the aerospace industry

Use Case: Cross-company Supply Chain Management (SCM) in the aerospace industry

This logistics use case was presented by Hanse Aerospace, the Germany's largest business association for SMEs in the aviation industry. The European aerospace industry has made an attempt to stage a pilot for a European Factory Platform (EFPF project). The goal was to different and already existing smart factory platforms (DIGICOR, NIMBLE, COMPOSITION, vfOS) for holistic SCM

offerings to companies in the aerospace industry. The approach made an attempt to organise logistics chains and freight transport across the actors in the supply chain (OEMs, 1st tier and 2nd tier suppliers) depending in the real-time demand of the production process. 30 partners from 11 European partner were involved in this project. The goal of the EFPF is automation of processes in the control of supply chains, also across the involved companies. After the completion of the EFPF project in 2023, the platform is now operated by the European Factory Foundation. One use case in the EFPF project, which has been prototypically implemented in SMEs, was “Aerospace Supply chain Digitalisation”. One pilot functionality is for example the EFPF Stock Level Monitoring which automatically monitors the availability of material at different production places with sensors (scales) at the Edge and issues transport orders. A control unit processes data locally and sends it to the Platform via the Internet. The application contributes to inventory transparency throughout the supply chain and avoids stock shortages and inventory differences. Reorders are automatically retriggered. 15 further technical solutions like this were developed in the project.

The full implementation of platform functions in Europe is challenging and has the potential for a large-scale pilot. The platform is ready for upscaling and transfer. It is a remarkable success that information exchange between OEMs and SME suppliers could be demonstrated.

Figure 4: SCM in the Logistics of Airplane Production – Source: Hanse Aerospace

Observations on Market Pathways:

The full-sale implementation off cross-company platforms in SCM is still a challenge due to several reasons:

- 🏠 The evaluation of the EFPF showed that 50% time savings and 20% cost savings in supply chain operations are possible.
- 🏠 Supplier policies of large OEMs in the aerospace industry (like Airbus and Boeing) are very restrictive for collaboration with small companies and supplier networks for **safety and security** reasons. Usually they do not use open platforms.

- 🏠 **Complex and highly customised products** lead to complex production and supply networks with slow step and execution of supplier management processes, particularly for small, new and ad-hoc suppliers. As a result, a direct connection of the IT systems has almost been impossible.
- 🏠 The formalisation and support for **collaboration rules** means (governance) by technical collaboration platforms are weak. There is a need for improvement.
- 🏠 The suppliers are **weakly integrated** in legacy IT systems of the OEMs (no real-time, missing features like collaborative planning and control). IT standards need to be strengthened and open, accepted platforms a needed.
- 🏠 SME within the supply chain need to be included in the decisions of the large manufacturers and 1st tier suppliers.

There is a further need to develop open ICT platforms, tools and service to support collaboration networks using Industry 4.0 methods and means.

New business models for operation and further maintenance are necessary and platform tools and serves need to be improved.

Open collaboration platforms are needed to improve speedy setup and operation.

Governance rules and procedures for collaboration in production networks and a knowledge protection model for ad-hoc collaboration in SME-clusters and beyond need to be introduced.

4.5 Observations from further Use Cases

During the interviews and workshops we also had some insights into two further use cases. Selected aspects concerning market pathways will be stated hereafter:

Automated Shipping:

Pratexo, a start-up company from 2021 in the field of Cloud-edge computing suggests a CEI use case for operation of automated ships on the basis of ship-based micro clouds. All IT applications on the ship will run on a common platform which is a marketplace for the available data which is used to support all applications on board. This concerns integrated ship operation systems, intelligent voyage optimisation, predictive maintenance management as well as connected supply chains. The shipping fleets are operated by distant, centralised clouds. The system is offered by Pratexo based on the Pratexo Edge Computing Cloud in co-operation with the Norwegian Telenor Maritime. The solution addresses ship owners, operators, solution providers and other industry stakeholders (<https://pratexo.com/shipping-on-the-edge/>).

Pratexo promises cost reductions based on the multiple use of data from the ship-based micro-cloud. Furthermore, ship owners and operators can gain cost reductions based on predictive maintenance, a reduce crew and optimised ship operations. Apart from this, the carbon footprint of shipping operations can be reduced on the basis of optimised ship operation. ABB is nowadays a main investor in Pratexo.

Camera-based traffic data detection by Teledyne FLIR in urban road traffic:

The application provides real-time road traffic data (travel times, traffic counting, vehicle classification), especially in urban areas. For this purpose, the system uses infrared cameras as sensors which use analysis software traffic data detection. The use of infrared technology is a clear advantage compared with daylight cameras for privacy reasons. So, the system was quite successful in Germany where data protection rules are quite strict. Data is collected on cloud servers where it is analysed in order to use is for traffic situation overviews and prediction as well as for urban transport planning purposes. This may be agent-based simulation approaches, also using AI.

Driverless Bus Shuttles from Easymile

This use case concerns the development of driverless shuttle buses. This application is up to now – at least for the deployment on public roads – still in a pilot stage with limited permissions. Easymile is a leading supplier of driverless shuttle buses in Europe. Currently, however, there is no market for autonomous vehicles.

Easymile uses service from the AWS data centre, but a close co-operation in common application is not foreseen. The company stresses that it is important to use the know-how from international hyperscalers, but it is likewise important for Europe to develop own approaches on this basis. A co-operation with big-tech players would not be too fruitful for European players. Global hyperscalers are too advanced in the field of cloud services. Europe needs own approaches.

Germany, for example, has very well analysed regulations (German Automated Driving Act) for automated driving inspired by the principle “safety first”. This is unique in the world. A further promising aspect is the development of intelligent vehicle sensors and software for automated vehicles. These European advantages must be used.

Functions for automated driving based on CEI, have not yet been conceived by Easymile. Functions which touch the functional safety of a fully automated vehicle will never be trusted to a cloud hyperscaler.

5 Conclusions

The political goals concerning CEI development in the mobility sector is to strengthen the CEI Continuum with and to promote European actors in the chain as much as possible. We have seen examples for successful and/or promising CEI applications in the European Mobility sector.

The international big-tech players are also active in the European Mobility sector. They mainly offer cloud services and they have considerable experience in this field. The gap is considerable and it hardly makes sense to build own European capacities here. But, the engagement of hyperscalers is typically not too sector specific. Here, the European Edge developers can compete if they keep and develop their know-how and capitalise on the new technological trends. The combination of sector-specific software/ hardware know-how in combination with control over (open) data flows is an opportunity.

The chance for Europe is development of intelligent Edge solutions which are based on the sector-specific know-how of the mobility related IT industry. CEI solutions are often brought into the market by sector-specific IT companies. One driver is the software application for use cases, the CEI architecture follows. The chance is the sector specific IT know-how of the European industry.

End users are rarely the players who ask for CEI applications. They are mostly offered by the sector specific hardware/ software solution providers. However, end users are important for the definition of the requirements on specific solutions.

We could see different approaches for the implementation of edge solutions:

- 🏠 Example Continental: Co-operation with a close global Hyperscaler is sought for the implementation of cloud services. Edge solutions are operated by Continental as owner of the specific know-how in vehicle electronics.
- 🏠 Example Pratexo: A globally established start-up in the field of edge computing implements applications in different sectors in co-operation with specialised industry players. Cloud services are bought as a side service.
- 🏠 Example consider it: An innovative, highly specialised European SME builds services on the edge including hardware and software. Cloud services are bought as a side service if needed.

All approaches seem to be practical. The last example seems to be an approach for a “pure” European solution.

It is important to guarantee access to data spaces, open data and standardised interfaces. This is easier to be implemented in the public sector than in the private industry.

We have seen the following obvious risks and dependencies:

The co-operation between hyperscalers and the sector-specific industry which provides Edge solutions contains the risk for European providers to loose know-how. On the other hand, the cloud services of the hyperscalers are sophisticated and the use of their products is efficient. The potential for European Edge providers is the development of sector-specific solutions and to protect the newly developed know-how: Use the cloud functions as tools and develop new sector-specific Edge-Know-how.

In the mobility sector, we can find a large public user groups (municipalities, administrations etc.). They have recognised the risk of data misuse, uncontrolled re-use and limited access rights. So they have a strong interest in open data and open interfaces. Furthermore, they are often against the transfer of data internationally and data processing on international servers. They want to protect their data and they are interested in having control over the use of data. These users often support regulations concerning open solutions and data protection in regulations, contracts and funding conditions.

